

Speculation on Scaling, Maximum Entropy and Free Particle Quantum Mechanics Part 2

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In Part I, we suggested that a particle at rest with mass, m_0 , has a sense of time because there is a probability for it to decay (i.e. undergo some kind of internal interaction). We argued that for maximum entropy (minimum information) this probability is proportional to the rest mass. This suggests that the frequency for a probability event in space is proportional to $1/m_0$. Using a Lorentz transformation, one has the Lorentz invariant $-Et+px$ suggesting a period of \hbar/E and a wavelength of \hbar/p .

Here, we suggest that the wavelength, like rest mass m_0 , is linked with a probabilistic event, but this time in space. As a consequence, different constant p values represent different probabilities for an internal spatial event and so even though one has constant motion, p is linked to different spatial probabilities. In classical physics, one simply assigns a probability to an event, e.g. heads or tails for a coin.

This idea of spatial probability seems to have consequences if p suddenly changes in space as in the case of an n_1 - n_2 index of refraction junction. There is discontinuity of velocity and p (momentum) at such a junction and one has p_1 before and p_2 after. Each p is linked with a spatial probability, but as one approaches the junction point from the left and right, this probability should become the same. In other words, the probability linked with momentum must be conserved at the junction point.

If one were only to have an incident p_1 and a second p_2 beam in one dimension, then each has a probability proportional to p (like m_0), but this suggests different amplitudes for each because $p_1 < p_2$ for $n_1 < n_2$. This cannot be, however, if the beam is not being augmented or attenuated and so one must postulate a reflected beam. In such a case, one deals with two kinds of balances, one related to the beam and the other with the spatial probability linked to p . These two equations may be multiplied to find the probability to reflect and refract.

Momentum as a Spatial Probability

The main argument of Part I is that a rest mass, m_0 , is proportional to a probability for an internal event in time. Doubling the rest mass doubles the probability. This extends to E and p as seen by the Lorentz invariant $-Et+px$ as argued in Part I. Thus, we suggest that p (momentum) does not just represent an impulse, but also a probability in space linked to an internal interaction. In other words, even though two particles may have different rest masses and velocities and are moving smoothly in space, it is momentum p which represents a probability for an internal spatial event, just as m_0 was proportional to a probability for an internal temporal event. This seems to be a somewhat unusual feature because in classical physics one simply assigns a probability to an event such as heads up or down for a coin.

The idea of a spatial probability proportional to p has consequences if p changes suddenly in space as we now argue.

One Dimensional Reflection-Refraction

Consider a particle/photon with momentum p which encounters an n_1 - n_2 index of refraction boundary at x_0 . At first, one may not consider the change in p as having anything to do with probability, but we argue it is proportional to an internal spatial probability. This has consequences as one may move towards x_0 from the left with p_1 or from the right with p_2 . At x_0 , one cannot have two different p related probabilities. This would then suggest giving different amplitudes to p_1 and p_2 , but that means physically diminishing or increasing the particle/photon beam which is not allowed.

As a result, one must postulate a reflected photon/particle. In such a case, one has probabilities linked to p in space, but also a balance of beam weights. This leads to two related equations. We use the variable A, B, C to represent weights linked to the incident, reflected and refracted beams. Ultimately, one may set $A=1$.

An equation representing a balance of the beams on each side of the x_0 yields:

$$A + B = C \quad ((1))$$

If $C < A$, then B must be negative which is what occurs for $n_2 > n_1$. Thus, A and B are not probabilities in the usual sense or flux etc. They are simply math weights that are associated with a balance.

We argue in this note, however, that p represents spatial probability and so too must be balanced at x_0 , i.e.

$$Ap_1 - p_1B = Cp_2 \quad ((2))$$

One may set $A = 1$ and solve for B and C in terms of p_1, p_2 .

Multiplying ((1)) and ((2)) together yields:

$$p_1(AA - BB) = p_2CC \quad ((3))$$

One may set $AA=1$ and then BB and CC represent classical probabilities for reflection and refraction.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the main point we wish to suggest is that momentum, in addition to representing impulse, should be thought of as a spatial probability for an internal interaction event, like m_0 is proportional to the probability for a temporal internal event.. Doubling rest mass doubles probability. Given that a rest mass transforms such that one has the Lorentz invariant: $A = -Et + px$, we suggest that this probability idea may be applied to E being proportional to an internal probability for a temporal event and p , for a spatial one.

We argue that p being proportional to a probability has consequences if p changes suddenly in space as in one dimensional reflection-refraction with an n_1 - n_2 index of refraction junction at x_0 . Spatial probability proportional to p must be the same as one approaches x_0 from the left or right, but one has p_1 or p_2 . This suggests changing their weights, but this means beam attenuation or augmentation, which is not allowed. Thus, one postulates a reflected beam. Then one has two balance equations, one linked to the beam and the other to spatial probability related to momentum. The first balance equation is mathematical and does not represent probability or flux, i.e. $A+B=C$ where A, B, C represent the incident, reflected and refracted beams. If $A=1$ and $C<1$, then $B<0$ showing that these are math weights. A spatial probability balance, with probability proportional to p , is: $A p_1 - p_1 B = p_2 C$. This allows one to set $A=1$ and solve for B and C . Multiplying the two equations yields: $p_1 (AA-BB) = p_2 CC$ which is a classical probability equation. (One may note that using the continuity of $\exp(ipx)$ and its first derivative leads to the same result, but here we wish to link p in p_x to probability.)